

TREATMENT OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND FIRST AID**Tohirova Jayrona Izzatillo qizi**

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Abstract. This article discusses the treatment of myocardial infarction and first aid. Detailed information is also provided on a number of factors that significantly increase the risk of developing an acute disease, and how the symptoms of myocardial infarction manifest themselves in detail. In particular, it carries a call to adhere to a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords: risk factors for myocardial infarction, signs and symptoms of myocardial infarction, atypical forms of myocardial infarction, treatment of myocardial infarction, complications of myocardial infarction, prevention of myocardial infarction.

ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ИНФАРКТА МИОКАРДА И ОКАЗАНИЕ ПЕРВОЙ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы лечения инфаркта миокарда и оказания первой медицинской помощи. Также представлена подробная информация о ряде факторов, которые значительно повышают риск развития острого заболевания, и о том, как подробно проявляются симптомы инфаркта миокарда. В том числе несёт собой призыв придерживаться здорового образа жизни.

Ключевые слова: факторы риска инфаркта миокарда, признаки и симптомы инфаркта миокарда, атипичные формы инфаркта миокарда, лечение инфаркта миокарда, осложнения инфаркта миокарда, профилактика инфаркта миокарда.

INTRODUCTION

Myocardial infarction - cardiovascular disease; As a result of the coronary circulatory disorders (arteries, thrombosis, spasm) is formed in the heart muscle. Myocardial infarction is caused by hypertension, diabetes, obesity, fascal, low-efficiency, physical and mental stress. In many cases myocardial infarction occurs on the grounds of stenocardia. One of the main symptoms of the Myocardial infarction is a particular part of the heart muscle to the development of long-term severe pain in the field of chest due to decrease in oxygen and nutrients. Bitter-heading pain (covering), in the center of the chest (steaming) or in the left half, often spreads to the side of the bottom, right, left, back, lower jaws. The pain will only last for several hours, sometimes even a day, relax, the cold sweat press, death, breath of heart activity, blood and electrocondandardiogram (ECG). Other diseases that cross pain attacks may also be changes in ECG. Therefore, only the doctor must draw conclusions by analyzing the patient's examination results. Myocardial infarction often occurs during the rapid work of the heart ischemic, in which stenocardic attacks intensify and often repeated. This will last a period of infarction and last for several weeks. During this period, if the doctor is addressed, myocardial infarction can be prevented.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Myocardial Infarction - One of the visions of myocardium is a limited necrosis of heart muscles and causes its blood supply and the acute violation of the balance between the blood supply and the demand. On its basis, atherosclerosis of the crown, spasm and atherosclerotic patterns is

lying blood transfusions. Its main reason is atherosclerosis in 95% of cases. In heart muscles, the following three cases can cause the development of acute necrosis.

Risk factors of infarction

- There are a number of factors that significantly increase the risk of development of this acute illness:

- Atherosclerosis. As a result of malfunction of the exchange, the emergence of Atherosclerotic Pillars in the vascular wall is a major risk in the development of myocardial infarction.

- Young. After 45-50, the risk of developing disease development will increase.

- Rock. According to statistics, this critical situation is 1.5 times more common than men, especially during the time of Klimax, the risk of developing myocardial infarction.

Artery hypertension. People with hypertension (high blood pressure) in human beings will be high-risk development, as it increases oxygen in myocardium.

RESULTS

The myocardial infarction experienced first, even though it is even smaller scale.

Smoking. This harmful habit leads to the failure of many organs and systems of our body. As a result of chronic nicotine poisoning, the crown arteries narrow, which leads to the lack of oxygen in myocardium. And it is not only about active smoking, but also about smoking.

Obesity and hypodynamia. When fat metabolism is damaged, the development of atherosclerosis is accelerated, and the risk of suitable diabetes increases. The physical insissibility and infarctomatically affect metabolism in the body, which leads to the accumulation of overweight.

Diabetes with sugar. In patients with diabetes, the myocardial infarction affects the development of the vascular walls and hemoglobin as a result of the hemoglobin, which is deteriorating its transportation.

Symptoms and symptoms of myocardial infarction. This sharp situation has its own features, and they are usually so clear that they may not be felt. Nevertheless, it is necessary to remember that there are also atypic forms of this disease.

Signs of EKG: rhythm sinus, 60 and fewer in Yus in a minute. The range of R-R is the same and expanded (when it comes with the sinus arrhalmia, the R-R is different). The amplitude in all networks is maintained to R to Teka and its QRS complex and sequence. RQ interval 0.12-0.22 sec. submerged to. Segmey moves slightly above the midline, and t tea amplitude may have increased. Sharp steps

- 1. A pyramid or tent-shaped T-wave (as a result of the delay in internal layer rePolsemia) - the first stage

- 2. Ingestion of the insolescence and the rise of the st segment of the STATION (with a diastolic and systolic flow) - transmural ischemia

- 3. Tavi's inversion (delayed dependarization) - the intermediate stage

- 4. Quality of the wave 4. Miaocardial necrosis - Intermediate step Chronic stages

- 5. Normalization of segment of ST items (next stage)

- 6. Normalization of the wave of t (chronic stage).

Atypic forms of myocardial infarction. The myocardial infarction, which is taking anticipent diagnosis, can cause a doctor to diagnose.

The gastritis option. The pain syndrome, which occurs in this form of illness, is similar to the pain due to the hassertitis and is located in the epelolik region. In the examination, the muscles of the front wall of the abdominal wall may be observed. Typically, such a form of myocardial infarction occurs in the lower left ventricular injuries that are close to diaphragga.

Asthic option. Reminiscent of a violent attack of bronchial asthma. Choking in the patient, foamy sputum (may also be dry) and at the same time does not look at the pain syndrome, not observed or weakly expressed. In difficult situations, the lung swell can develop. When examination, the disease of heart rhythm, low blood pressure, can be felt in the lungs. Often, the poorest form occurs at the background of repeated myocardial infarctions, as well as a heavy cardiosclerosis.

Arthmic option. This form of myocardial infarction is manifested in various arithmias (extrasismoliya, blinking illicacy or paracsy tachycardia) or in different levels of attricular units. The reason for the violation of the heartbreaker may not be determined by myocardial infarction in the EKG check.

A cerebral option. Characterized by breeding circulation of blood circulation. Patients can be dizzy, headache, nausea, and vomiting, can be complained about the weakness of the feet.

A painless option (shape). This form of myocardial infarction will be the most common cause for the challenges in diagnosis. The pain syndrome may not be observed at all, patients complain about unknown discomfort and extreme deafness. Often this disease occurs in patients with diabetes and is very difficult.

DISCUSSION

Sometimes the clinical image of the myocardial infasion there is symptoms of various diseases, and in such cases, unfortunately, the end of the situation will be more negative.

Treatment of myocardial infarction

The patient can doubt myocardium infarction, if:

If the pain that crosses a strong combined feeling behind the chest, it lasts more than 5-10 minutes;

Pain does not calm in the peaceful situation or after receiving nitrogenicserin;

Pain comes with strong weakness, nausea, vomiting, headache and dizziness.

If you doubt myocardial infarction, call an ambulance immediately and start helping the patient. The patient as the first assistance to the patient is given early, and the constant will be positive.

The cargo falling into the heart should be reduced, so the patient should be lifted up a little head. Ensuring the access of clean air and try to calm the patient, it is possible to give sedatives.

The patient should chew a nitrogliserin tablet (pre-crush) and a single aspirin tablet.

If the drug is available in a bubble-blockator group (atenolol, Methoprololol), to chew the patient (it doesn't mean it's not possible) 1 tablet. If the patient regularly accepts this medicine, then the extraorde dose of medicines should be borne.

To reduce pain, the patient should be given an analgesic drug (analgin, bargain, etc.).

In addition, the patient can drink a tablet panangin or 60 drops of corn.

If heart stop is suspected (fainty, breathing cessation, no response to the absence of breaths and the absence of pulse) should be initiated. If the patient is not conscious, the treatments should be continued until doctors arrive.

Dangerous aspects

lung tumor;

Cardogenic shock;

death (death from a heart attack occurs in 35% of cases)

Preventive

Careful treatment of chronic diseases;

body weight supervision;

to abandon malicious habits;

to control psychological and physical stress.

Jeopardy group

patients with diabetes and hypertension;

People who have experienced heart ischemic and painted by stenocardium;

patients with an excess body weight;

smokers and drinkers.

CONCLUSIONS

Prevention of myocardial infarction. Control the amount of cholesterol in the blood. All people aged 45 are recommended to regularly monitor fat metabolism, as it is one of the main causes of cardiovascular disease that develops in violation.

Blood pressure control. The blood pressure is constantly 140/90 mm. wire. top. As above, it is required to normalize medicines, as the load that falls into the heart with arterial hypertension significantly increases.

Control of blood glucose levels. It is necessary to determine the disorders of carbohydrate metabolism and prevent diabetes.

Diet. It is recommended to limit food consumption, including food salt, large amounts of cholesterol and difficult-free oils. The diet should include vegetable fibers, vitamins and minerals, sea products.

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